

Batteries & Supercaps

Supporting Information

Recessed Microelectrodes as a Platform to Investigate the Intrinsic Redox Process of Prussian Blue Analogs for Energy Storage Application

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Supporting information

Recessed microelectrodes as a platform to investigate the intrinsic redox process of Prussian-Blue Analogs for energy storage application.

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S1. Characterization of recessed microelectrode

The qualitative characterization of the geometry of the recessed microelectrode was performed using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and the depth was determined using electrochemical methods; namely cyclic voltammetry (CV) in the presence of a redox mediator to determine the diffusion-limited current of the empty recessed microelectrode.

The CV was performed in the presence of 5 mM hexaammineruthenium trichloride $[\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_6]\text{Cl}_3$ in 0.1 M KCl with a scan rate of 10 mV/s. The diffusion-limited current i_{lim} was used to estimate the cavity depth (h) using the equation S1.^[53] Where the number of electrons transferred during the reduction of the redox mediator is $n = 1$, $F = 96,485 \text{ C mol}^{-1}$ is the Faraday constant, C is the concentration of the redox mediator, $D = 9.1 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ is the diffusion coefficient of the redox mediator, r is the radius of the electrode and h is the cavity depth. The electrochemical approach to calculate the recession depth resulted in $h = 16.7 \mu\text{m}$.

$$I_{\text{lim}} = \frac{4\pi n F C D r^2}{4h + \pi r} \quad \text{Equation S1}$$

Figure S1.1. Evaluating the depth of the recessed microelectrode, a) Cyclic voltammograms recorded with a scan rate of 10 mV/s in 5 mM $[\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_6]\text{Cl}_3$ in 0.1 M KCl. The red curve was recorded using a disc-shaped, not recessed $100 \mu\text{m}$ Au microelectrode, and the black curve using a recessed $100 \mu\text{m}$ Au microelectrode. b) SEM image of a recessed $100 \mu\text{m}$ gold microelectrode.

A custom-built 3-D-printed electrochemical cell was designed to accommodate the upside-down placement of the working electrode (WE) and to enable a closed setup by sealing it with a gasket to avoid electrolyte evaporation.

Figure S1.2. Optical microscope images of a recessed Au microelectrode. a) Recessed microelectrode before filling the cavity, and b) after filling the cavity. c) Closed electrochemical cell: three-electrode set-up where the working electrode (WE) was the recessed microelectrode, the counter electrode (CE) a Pt wire, and the reference electrode (RE) a Ag/AgCl/3 M KCl electrode.

All measurements were performed using the same recessed microelectrode (rME) to ensure the same depth of the cavity. Before each experiment, the rME was washed and cleaned by sonication for 20 minutes in isopropyl alcohol and deionized water. The gold rME was electrochemically cycled in 0.5 M H₂SO₄ to evaluate the gold redox process and to remove any absorbed residual.

Control voltammograms were performed in the electrolytes of interest using the empty rME to evaluate i) any presence of active material (PBA) inside the cavity after the cleaning procedure, and ii) additional electrochemical reversible processes in the used potential range.

Figure S1.3. Cyclic voltammogram obtained with the empty rME at a scan rate of 100 mV s⁻¹ in a) 5 M NaClO₄, b) 5 M NaSCN. The potential windows covering the range of interest of the experiments performed after filling the rME with the PBA.

S2: NiHCF characterization and electrochemical performance

Figure S2.1. $Ni[Fe(CN)_6]$ nanoparticles a) SEM image, b) XRD pattern and Le Bail fitting.

Figure S2.2. Galvanostatic charging of a rME filled with NiHCF in 5 M NaClO₄ at different C-rates a) 3C, b) 9C, c) 12C, d) 18C, e) 26C, and f) 70C.

S3 MnHCF characterization and electrochemical performance

Figure S3.1. Mn[Fe(CN)₆] nanoparticles. A) SEM image and crystal structure of the MnHCF nanoparticles. B) XRD patterns of the MnHCF nanoparticles compared with the predicted cubic structure (reference was calculated with Vesta).

In 5 M NaClO₄ as electrolyte, the charge was calculated by integrating the cyclic voltammograms for different cycles. The Autolab Nova software was used to plot the time vs current of the CVs and to integrate the charge.

Figure S3.2. Cyclic voltammogram at 100 mV/s in 5 M NaClO₄. Arrows indicate increasing cycle numbers.

Figure S3.3. MnHCF electrochemical performance recorded in 5 M NaClO₄. a) 3000 consecutive CVs recorded with a scan rate of 100 mV/s plotted as current response vs time. b) Enlarged portion shows the oxidation peak of selected cycles.

Figure S3.4. Optical microscope images of MnHCF@rME a) before and b) after electrochemical cycling in 5 M NaClO₄.

Figure S3.5. Raman spectroscopy set-up. a) Control analysis on a glassy carbon (GC) surface. b) Cell design for operando microelectrochemical Raman spectroscopy using the PBA@rME platform.

S4 Characterization of $K_2Mn[Mn(CN)_6]$ (MnHCMn) nanoparticles

Figure S4.1. A) SEM image and crystal structure of MnHCMn nanoparticles. B) XRD patterns of MnHCMn nanoparticles compared with the monoclinic predicted structure (reference was calculated with Vesta).

Electrochemical performance of MnHCMn

Figure S4.2. Scheme of the electrochemical setup inside a glass chamber to provide an inert environment. The Ar flow was wetted in a pre-chamber with distilled water (not shown).

Electrolyte screening for MnHCMn was performed in Na⁺-based electrolytes using CV in 1 M NaClO₄, NaCl, and NaSCN. Galvanostatic cycling shows different charging profiles in each electrolyte at an applied current of 20 nA. In 1 M NaClO₄ charging did not reach a full charge in the limit of -0.6 to -1.2 V. In 1 M NaSCN, NaCl, and NaClO₄ all measurements showed a fast discharge.

Figure S4.3. MnHCMn@rME electrolyte screening. CVs performed at 100 mV/s in a) 1 M NaClO₄, c) 1 M NaSCN, and e) 1 M NaCl. Arrows indicate increasing voltammetric cycles from the 1st cycle to the 1500th cycle. Galvanostatic cycling at an applied current of 20 nA. b) 1 M NaClO₄, d) 1 M NaSCN, and f) 1 M NaCl.

Figure S4.4. Optical microscope images of a rME filled with MnHCMn. a) Before and after cycling in b) 1 M NaClO₄, c) 1 M NaCl and d) 1 M NaSCN.

The influence of the electrolyte concentration was investigated using MnHCMn and performing testing the material at around 20°C. The charging and discharging ratio were increasing with increasing concentrations. In 1 M NaSCN the first cycle had an efficiency of around 52%, b) in 5 M NaSCN the efficiency was around 47%, whereas at c) 10 M NaSCN it increased to around 74 %.

Figure S4.5. CVs obtained with MnHCMn@rME at different scan rates in a) 1 M NaSCN, b) 5 M NaSCN, c) 10 M NaSCN. d) Peak current (i_p) versus square root of the scan rate. (stars: anodic peak current (i_{pa}), circles: cathodic peak current (i_{pc})).

Table S4.1. Linear fit from Figure S4.5 d).

Electrolyte	i peak	Slope	R ²
1 M NaSCN	cathodic currents	-7.20E-6	0.991
1 M NaSCN	anodic currents	+4.99E-6	0.982
5 M NaSCN	cathodic currents	-5.14E-6	0.998
5 M NaSCN	anodic currents	+4.97E-6	0.997
10 M NaSCN	cathodic currents	-1.85E-6	0.978
10 M NaSCN	anodic currents	+1.55E-6	0.892

Figure S4.6. MnHCMn galvanostatic cycling charged at around 20C in NaSCN at different concentrations a) 1 M, b) 5 M, and c) 10 M.

The capacity vs potential curve showed an opposite trend compared with the %CE. In 1 M NaSCN a high capacity was retained from cycles 1 to 20. In a high concentration NaSCN of 10 M the capacity reached 100 times less than in 1 M.

Figure S4.7. a) Capacity at cycle 10 at different electrolyte concentrations at 20C. b) Capacity at cycle 10 in dependence of the NaSCN concentration.

Effect of the presence of O₂ on the MnHCMn redox process

Figure S4.8 a) CVs in 10 M NaSCN recorded with a scan rate of 100 mV/s under Ar atmosphere (black) and O₂ purged electrolyte (red). b) Galvanostatic charging at 24C in O₂ purged electrolyte. c) CE% comparison of Ar and O₂ containing electrolytes.

[53] E. Torralba, E. Laborda, A. Molina, C. Cachet-Vivier, S. Bastide, *ChemElectroChem* **2021**, 8, 735–744.